

Thermal Decomposition of Benzhydrol over Alumina*

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The thermal decomposition of benzhydrol over Al_2O_3 impregnated with varying amounts of Na_2CO_3 was studied at 290 and at 400°. At 290°, on the pure (unimpregnated) Al_2O_3 the major reaction was a disproportionation leading to benzophenone, diphenylmethane and water. Hydrogen formation increased as the Na^+ -content of the catalyst was increased. Hydrogenolysis of benzhydrol by externally supplied hydrogen was shown to be absent at 290°, but did take place at 400°. A hydride transfer mechanism has been proposed for the disproportionation reaction.

THE ability of alumina to catalyse the cross-disproportionation of alcohols and carbonyl compounds has recently been reported^{1,2}. In this reaction there is the transfer of a hydride ion from an adsorbed alcohol molecule to an adsorbed carbonyl compound and the overall effect of the reaction is the dehydrogenation of the alcohol by a hydrogen acceptor, namely, the carbonyl compound. An example is the transfer dehydrogenation of the cyclohexanol by acetone :

The above reaction is mechanistically significant in the sense that alumina, normally a poor dehydrogenation catalyst, can cause the dehydrogenation of alcohols if a hydride acceptor is present on the surface. The reaction of benzhydrol over alumina to form benzophenone, diphenylmethane and water is reported in the present paper as another example of a similar reaction, where the potential carbonium ion derived from the alcohol itself acts as the hydride acceptor.

Experimental

Alumina was prepared by the hydrolysis of aluminium isopropoxide and calcined at 600° for 6 hr. $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Na}^+$ catalysts were prepared by shaking weighed samples of alumina with sodium carbonate solutions of known strength for 6 hr and after centrifugation, calcining the residue at 600° for 6 hr in a stream of nitrogen. The amount of Na^+ adsorbed by the alumina was estimated by determining the Na_2CO_3 -content of the supernatant liquid after impregnation.

One gram of the catalyst was taken in a pyrex reactor tube kept in a slanting position in an electrically heated tube furnace. A column of glass beads

above the catalyst acted as a preheater zone for the reaction mixture. Provision was available for measuring the temperature of the catalyst bed during the reaction. The catalyst was activated by passing a stream of dry air at 500° for 3 hr followed by dry oxygen-free nitrogen at the reaction temperature for 1 hr. before starting the reaction. The liquid reaction mixture, a 20% w/v solution of benzhydrol in benzene, was introduced from the top of the reactor at the required rate by means of a syringe pump. The liquid products were collected in suitably cooled traps and the gas, in a gas burette over saturated brine. It was found that all the organic material introduced could not be recovered in this manner because some of the products/reagents are strongly adsorbed by the catalyst and cannot be stripped out at the reaction temperature. This adsorbed material was released by raising the temperature of the reactor, after the reaction, to 500° and passing 5 ml of benzene along with nitrogen. When the fraction so collected was combined with the earlier fraction, satisfactory material balance could be obtained. Alternately, after the reaction, the reactor tube was cooled and the contents, including the catalyst, was rinsed thrice with ether and the washings were combined with the original fraction and analyzed. The composition of the product obtained by the two methods were identical. The fraction stripped out at 500° was richer in benzophenone than the earlier fraction, showing that benzophenone is more strongly adsorbed by the catalyst than diphenylmethane. This effect was more on the catalysts with higher Na^+ -contents. For estimating the actual product distributions, the fraction collected at 500° was combined with the earlier fraction and the data given in Table I, correspond to the analysis of this combined lot.

Analysis of Products :

Analysis of liquid products was carried out by gas chromatography using an Aerograph Gas Chromatograph, Model 90-P-3, having a thermal conductivity detector with tungsten-rhenium filaments. Liquid

* Hydrogen Transfer Reactions : Part III; for Part II, See reference 2.

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TABLE I. THERMAL DECOMPOSITION OF BENZHYDROL OVER ALUMINA AT 290°.

Experi- ment No.	Catalyst ^(a)	Wt. of benzhy- drol used, g. ^(b)	H ₂ (ml)/NTP ^(c)	Analysis of the reaction product			Total Wt. of product accounted for, g.	Selectivity		Benzo- phenone (total)	Benzo- phenone (Disp) ^(g)	
				H ₂ O, g.	Benzophe- none, g.	Diphenyl- methane, g.		Benzhy- drol, g.	% Con- version ^(d)			Dehydro- genation ^(e)
1	None ^(h)	3.6	13.7	—	0.06	Nil	3.50	3.6	100.0	Nil	—	—
2	Al ₂ O ₃ (Pure)	3.6	14.7	detected	1.80	1.60	Nil	100.0	3.3	96.7	1.06	0.99
3	Al ₂ O ₃ / 0.09% Na ⁺	3.6	38.5	detected	2.00	1.50	0.04	98.9	8.8	91.2	1.19	1.00
4	Al ₂ O ₃ / 0.31% Na ⁺	3.6	36.7	detected	1.90	1.50	0.075	97.9	8.5	91.5	1.18	0.99
5	Al ₂ O ₃ / 0.51% Na ⁺	3.6	36.7	detected	1.53	1.14	0.82	77.5	10.7	89.3	1.23	0.99
6	Al ₂ O ₃ / 0.83% Na ⁺	3.6	47.6	detected	1.20	0.80	1.50	60.0	18.0	82.0	1.39	0.95
7	Al ₂ O ₃ / 1.57% Na ⁺	3.6	42.2	detected	1.13	0.75	1.50	56.4	16.9	83.1	1.39	0.95
8	Al ₂ O ₃ / 2.1% Na ⁺	3.6	38.5	detected	0.39	0.07	3.16	13.2	65.8	34.2	5.24	1.04
9	Al ₂ O ₃ (Pure)	18.3	71.5	0.8	9.00	7.80	0.55	97.0	3.3	96.7	1.06	0.99
10	Al ₂ O ₃ (pure) (400°)	3.6	22.0	detected	1.83	1.55	Nil	100.0	5.0	95.0	1.09	0.98
11	Al ₂ O ₃ ⁽ⁱ⁾ (pure)	3.6	—	detected	1.80	1.60	Nil	100.0	—	—	1.05	—
12	Al ₂ O ₃ ^(j) (pure) (400°)	3.6	—	detected	1.40	2.00	Nil	100.0	—	—	0.65	—

(a) One g. of the catalyst was used for each run. (b) A 20% w/v solution of benzhy-drol was passed at the rate of 40 ml/hr. (c) The gas collected during the reaction was identified to be hydrogen. (d) Based on unreacted benzhy-drol. (e) % of total conversion. Dehydrogenation+disproportionation = 100. (f) Calculated on the basis of the hydrogen collected. (g) Benzophenone (Disp) refers to moles of benzophenone formed by the disproportionation mechanism. It is obtained by subtracting the number of moles of benzophenone formed by dehydrogenation calculated on the basis of the H₂ collected, from the total moles of benzophenone formed. (h) The reactor tube was filled with pyrex glass beads. (i) Hydrogen at the rate of 15 ml/min was passed along with the benzhy-drol.

samples were introduced using a Hamilton micro-litre syringe. Components present in as low as 0.01% can be readily detected and estimated under the conditions of analysis.

Diphenylmethane, benzophenone and benzhydrol were analysed by GLPC on a 3'x1/4" column of 10% Carbowax-20 M on 60-80 mesh Chromosorb-W-AW-DMCS, at 200° with H₂ (120 ml/min) as carrier gas. Quantitative analysis was accomplished by applying calibration factors determined with the pure authentic components, to the respective peak areas. Water could be qualitatively detected by using the same column at 40° (80 ml/min H₂) or by using a 5'x1/4" Poropak-Q column at 130° (120 ml/min H₂). However, quantitative estimation of the water was not possible in most cases because the water formed an immiscible phase. In a large scale experiment (No. 9, Table 1) using pure alumina, where sufficient water was formed to enable the mechanical separation of the water layer, the formation of the theoretically expected amount of water could be confirmed. The gas formed in the reaction was volumetrically estimated and was identified as hydrogen by analysing on a Fisher-Hamilton Gas Partitioner (Model 29) using a 6' di-2-ethyl-hexyl sebacate column followed by a 6 1/2' Molecular Sieve 13X column in series. The results are presented in Table 1.

Discussion

Experiment 1 in Table 1 shows that benzhydrol decomposes thermally in the absence of a catalyst at 290° only to a slight extent, giving benzophenone and hydrogen. In the presence of catalyst, benzhydrol is decomposed to the extent ranging from 100% on pure alumina to 13% on Al₂O₃ containing 2.1% Na⁺. Gas formation progressively increases as the Na⁺-content of the catalyst is increased and there is a parallel increase in the benzophenone/diphenylmethane ratio. Increase in the dehydrogenation activity of alumina on impregnation by alkali has been reported earlier³. In the present case, on all the catalysts, the amount of benzophenone formed is far in excess of that expected from a simple dehydrogenation corresponding to the amount of hydrogen formed. By subtracting the number of moles of benzophenone formed by dehydrogenation as calculated on the basis of hydrogen formation, from the total number of moles of benzophenone formed, the number of moles of excess benzophenone formed is obtained. The ratio of this value to the number of moles of diphenylmethane formed is nearly unity. From this it can be concluded that the benzophenone is formed in two parallel reactions, one a simple dehydrogenation (1) and the other a type of disproportionation (2) :

An alternate possibility, namely, that diphenylmethane is formed by the hydrogenolysis of benzhydrol by the hydrogen formed in (1) can be ruled-out

on the basis of the results of experiment 11 in Table 1. Here, hydrogen was passed along with the benzhydrol and it can be seen that the benzophenone (total)/diphenylmethane ratio is nearly the same as when no hydrogen is passed (experiment 2). However at 400° in the presence of H₂ (experiment 12) the above ratio is much smaller than in the absence of hydrogen (experiment 10). Hence at 400° the direct hydrogenolysis of benzhydrol by molecular hydrogen does take place. Thus at 400° this mechanism will be an alternate path for diphenylmethane, but not at 290°. Benzophenone itself, when passed over alumina at 290° was unchanged and could be recovered quantitatively. From the results in Table 1 it can be seen that the major reaction (97% of total conversion) is disproportionation of benzhydrol according to (2) on the pure alumina.

The formation of toluene and benzaldehyde as products of the reaction of benzyl alcohol over alumina is known^{4,5}. During the high temperature decomposition of methanol over alumina, methane, CO and H₂ have been detected⁴. A general mechanism for such reactions, an adaptation of one proposed by Notari⁶, is depicted in figure 1. The first

Fig. 1. Disproportionation of Benzhydrol. (Large Circles : Occupied anion sites; Squares : Vacant anion sites; Thick dots : Al⁺⁺⁺ ions.)

step is visualised as a dissociative adsorption of benzhydrol over alumina to generate surface hydroxy and alkoxy groups. This is followed by hydride transfer and desorption of products. Studies are under progress to confirm this hydride transfer mechanism by deuterium labelling experiments.

The thermal decomposition of benzhydrol has been studied on thoria and magnesia also. On these catalysts the reaction is more complex than on alumina. Benzyl alcohol, benzaldehyde, benzene and toluene have also been detected as reaction

products. Details of these studies will be reported in a later communication.

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